

Genus *Crotalaria* XVI.¹ Pyrrolizidine Alkaloids of *C. leioloba* Bartl., *C. stipularia* Desv. and *C. tetragona* Roxb.

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Monocrotaline has been isolated from the seeds of *C. leioloba* Bartl. (Syn. *C. ferruginea* Wall.),² and *C. stipularia* Desv., whereas seeds of *C. tetragona* Roxb. have been found to contain integerrimine and trichodesmine.

IN recent years, considerable interest has been shown in the field of pyrrolizidine alkaloids because of their interesting biological activities.³ In this communication we wish to record the identification of pyrrolizidine alkaloids present in some of the species of genus *Crotalaria*.

Powdered seeds of *C. leioloba* representing 0.19% tertiary bases and 0.33% N-oxides and *C. stipularia* containing 0.68% tertiary bases and 0.02% their N-oxides, were defatted with petroleum ether and subsequently extracted with ethanol. The alcoholic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure, stirred with dilute (0.5N) sulphuric acid and filtered. The filtrate was washed with chloroform, basified with ammonia and again extracted with chloroform to give crude alkaloids. The crude mixture on TLC slurry made from silica gel G with N/10 sodium hydroxide, using solvent systems (a) methanol (b) chloroform-methanol-ammonia 85 : 14 : 1 and paper chromatography (solvent system was upper layer obtained by shaking *n*-butanol with equal volume of 5% acetic acid) showed mainly single spot having R_f values same as that of monocrotaline. The crude mixture on crystallisation from methanol afforded colourless crystals m.p. 197°-198°, undepressed on admixture with monocrotaline (Found : C, 59.35; H, 7.12; N, 4.29%; Calc. for $C_{16}H_{23}NO_6$)C, 59.06; H, 7.12; N, 4.31%). It readily formed picrate m.p. 236°-237° (Found : C, 47.75; H, 4.72; N, 10.37%; Calc. for $C_{16}H_{23}NO_6 \cdot C_6H_3N_3O_7$; C, 47.63; H, 4.71; N, 10.10%). The IR (KBr) of the compound was superimposable with that of authentic monocrotaline.

The seeds of *C. tetragona* Roxb. were collected from Darjeeling and Dehradun. The alkaloidal constituents of these two collections were different.

The seeds collected from Darjeeling on assay showed 0.19% tertiary bases and 0.02% N-oxides. The

seeds were processed as described earlier. The ammoniacal solution on extractions with pet. ether yielded a solid alkaloid, m.p. 169°-170°. The alkaloid on TLC and paper chromatography exhibited same R_f values as that of integerrimine. The m.p. was not depressed on admixture with authentic integerrimine. The identity was also confirmed by superimposable IR spectrum.

Seeds representing 0.13% tertiary bases and 0.03% N-oxides collected from Dehradun were similarly processed. The TLC pattern of alkaloids from this variety was different from that of Darjeeling collection. The crude alkaloid mixture obtained by shaking ammoniacal solution with chloroform was purified by passing through alumina column. The fractions eluted with benzene-chloroform (9 : 1) on further purification yielded a pure solid base, m.p. 160°-161°. Its TLC behaviour in different solvent systems was same as that of trichodesmine. The m.p. did not depress on admixture with authentic trichodesmine. The MS (M^+ 353) of the base revealed same cracking pattern⁴ as that of trichodesmine.

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References

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